

Design and Implementation of Adaptive Control Strategies for EMG-Based Multifunctional Prosthetic Hand

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ABSTRACT

People may lose their limbs due to various traumas, accidents, or health problems. Recently, significant advancements have been made to develop prosthetic systems that can replace missing limbs in order to mitigate the effects of such losses and improve individuals' quality of life. In this context, researchers have been conducting intensive studies in design and control to make prosthetic devices more functional and better compatible with the human body. In this study, bioelectrical signals were collected using surface electrodes placed on four different muscle regions through the surface electromyography (EMG) method. These collected signals were used to control a robotic hand system, produced as a five-fingered model via 3D printing technology. The finger and joint movements of the robotic hand were managed by a PID (Proportional-Integral-Derivative) control algorithm, which precisely controls the position of each motor. This method enabled intuitive and cognitive interaction between the user and the prosthetic hand, allowing real-time motion control through bioelectrical signals to be successfully achieved. The results demonstrate that EMG-based signal-driven prosthetic systems provide both a user-friendly and functional solution.

Keywords:

1. INTRODUCTION

People may lose one or more of their limbs due to various injuries, traffic accidents, or medical conditions. In such cases, robotic systems that can functionally and visually resemble the missing limb are developed. These systems are generally referred to as “prostheses” and are specifically named according to the limb they replace, such as arm prosthesis or leg prosthesis. The movement structure of human limbs is shaped by a highly complex anatomical arrangement. The number of joints in a limb determines the diversity of movements

possible in that region. An adult human skeleton consists of a total of 206 bones. Approximately 90 of these are located in the skull and facial area, mostly connected by immovable joints. Along the spine, 33 bones are connected by semi-mobile joints. Movable joints, which allow active movement, are primarily found in the arms and legs. Specifically examining the human hand, each finger has three joints, resulting in a total of fifteen joints. This corresponds to fourteen distinct independent axes of movement. Even excluding wrist motions, the hand's movement system is extremely complex and requires a high degree of control precision. Among the body's limbs, the hand possesses the greatest freedom of movement and complexity.

For a prosthetic system that replaces such a complex structure to be effectively used by the user, two fundamental factors are essential:

- The prosthetic hand must be mechanically designed in an ergonomic and functional manner.
- Advanced control mechanisms should be developed to enable precise control of the positions and velocities of the fingers and joints.

However, no matter how successful the mechanical design of the prosthetic hand is, achieving the desired performance is not possible unless the human-prosthesis interaction is cognitively established correctly. In other words, if the user's movement intention, type of movement (e.g., closing the hand, grasping with two fingers), and velocity information are not accurately conveyed to the prosthesis, the device cannot operate naturally and effectively. Voluntary muscle movements in the human body are carried out by bioelectrical signals transmitted from the central nervous system to the muscles. These signals are called electromyograms (EMG) and carry important information about the type, intensity, and activity of the muscles. The primary function of the biological hand is to grasp and hold objects. Wrist movements serve as secondary motions that support these functions. Therefore, the functionality of a prosthetic hand is largely related to the variety and controllability of finger movements. The greater the number of independent movements the prosthetic hand can perform, the closer its performance is to the natural biological hand. This study aims to create a database of the electrical activity of human hand muscles, develop an interface that facilitates interaction between the human and the prosthetic hand based on this data, and design both a simulation environment and control algorithms.

Figure 1. EMG-Based Multifunctional Prosthetic Arm

2. METHOD

2.1. ANATOMICAL STRUCTURE AND FUNCTIONAL OPERATION OF MUSCLES

Skeletal muscles are primarily composed of long, cylindrical muscle cells called muscle fibers. The length of these fibers ranges approximately from 1 to 50 mm, while their diameter varies between 10 and 100 micrometers. Each muscle fiber is covered by a semi-permeable membrane called the sarcolemma, which

surrounds the outer part of the fiber. This membrane regulates the internal environment of the cell and facilitates the transmission of stimuli. Muscle fibers attach to cartilage or bone tissues via tendons. Muscle contraction occurs as a result of the shortening of these fibers and their volumetric expansion (swelling). This biomechanical process enables the muscle to functionally contract and, consequently, facilitates the movement of the skeletal system.

2.2. PHYSIOLOGICAL MECHANISM OF MUSCLE CONTRACTION

Muscle tissues can contract in two primary ways in response to physiological stimuli: static (isometric) and dynamic (isotonic) contractions. In static contraction, the muscle length remains constant while only volumetric expansion (swelling) is observed. In contrast, during dynamic contractions, both muscle length shortens and muscle volume increases. In both cases, the muscle generates mechanical force in response to external loads. When a muscle cell receives a nerve stimulus, a brief contraction occurs first, followed by a relaxation phase. This mechanical activity is driven by a complex series of biochemical processes.

Figure 2. Illustration of the Muscle Contraction Mechanism in the Human Arm

When a muscle becomes active, glycogen reserves begin to break down to meet its energy demands. During cellular respiration, oxygen is consumed and carbon dioxide is released, while glycogen is first converted into pyruvic acid. In this transformation, energy carriers called ATP (adenosine triphosphate) molecules are generated. In the presence of sufficient oxygen, pyruvic acid is oxidized in the mitochondria and enters the citric acid cycle (Krebs cycle). As a result of this cycle, carbon dioxide (CO₂), water (H₂O), and additional ATP molecules are produced. However, under oxygen-deficient conditions, pyruvic acid is converted anaerobically into lactic acid, a process that produces a limited amount of energy. After exercise, the respiratory rate remains elevated for a period to repay the oxygen debt; during this time, some of the lactic acid is re-oxidized to generate energy. This energy is then used to convert the remaining lactic acid back into glycogen. During muscle activity, only about 25% of the produced energy is converted into mechanical work, while the majority is dissipated as heat. Therefore, muscle energy efficiency is low, but muscles indirectly contribute to maintaining body temperature. Communication between the nervous system and muscle cells occurs at specialized structures called motor end plates. Signals from motor neurons are transmitted to the muscle via the neurotransmitter acetylcholine at the synapse. This chemical stimulus initiates muscle contraction. In some types of smooth muscle, a different neurotransmitter called noradrenaline performs this function. Cardiac muscle differs from other muscle types as it primarily derives energy from fatty acids; thus, it is not directly affected by blood glucose levels. Smooth muscles envelop the organs they control in a network-like structure. Rhythmic and wave-like contractions of these muscles enable the transport of substances, especially in the digestive system, through movements known as peristalsis. Even when the body is completely at rest, some muscles maintain a low level of isometric contraction to help maintain posture against gravity. This muscle tone is vital for keeping postural balance.

2.3. NEUROMECHANICAL CONTROL OF VOLUNTARY MUSCLE MOVEMENTS

Motor nerves are structurally composed of nerve cells and transmit a binary signal (on/off) to motor end plates. This means each motor nerve can be in one of two states: active (polarized) or passive (depolarized). Consequently, each muscle fiber is either at rest or in an excited state. The fundamental characteristics of normal muscle movement are smoothness, continuity, and precision. These features largely depend on the fact that each muscle consists of multiple motor units. As the magnitude of movement increases, the number of recruited motor units also increases. Maximum muscle contraction occurs when all available motor units are activated, resulting in smoother motion. Additional smoothness in muscle movement can be achieved by controlling the number of muscle fibers stimulated per unit time. Although each motor unit can only produce contraction at a fixed level, the contraction frequency (i.e., the depolarization-repolarization rate of motor end plates) increases the total force generated by the muscle. This demonstrates that muscle movement is directly controlled both by the number of recruited motor units and their stimulation frequency.

Figure 3. Graded Muscle Response through Sequential Motor Unit Activation

2.4. CONTROL OF MUSCLES USING SERVO MECHANISMS

The nervous system that controls muscle movements essentially functions as a servo control mechanism, and a simplified block diagram of this system is presented in Figure 4. The system begins with sensory receptors that detect information from the environment and transmit it to the brain. The brain compares the incoming data with reference signals stored in memory and interprets the resulting difference as an error signal. This error signal is then sent to the muscle via motor nerves, regulating muscle movement accordingly.

Figure 4. Basic Block Diagram of the Nervous System Servo Mechanism Controlling Muscle Movement

For example, when a person touches their finger to a cold surface, the sensory receptors in the finger detect the cold and send the signal to the brain. Since the brain does not perceive this as a threat, the motor nerves do not send any response command to the muscles. However, if the finger comes into contact with a hot surface, the brain quickly processes this information (Scheme & Englehart, 2011). If the temperature is high, commands are sent via motor nerves to the muscles to rapidly withdraw the finger. There is a delay of a few hundred milliseconds between the stimulation of sensory receptors and the resulting muscle movement; the duration of this delay is directly related to the individual's attention and focus. In cases of extremely high temperature, a reflex mechanism is activated, causing the finger to withdraw from the hot surface in approximately 150 milliseconds. This reflex response is governed by an emergency signal gate located in the spinal cord, enabling a rapid reaction without the need for communication with the brain under normal circumstances. Strong stimuli cause the reflex gate to open, allowing muscles to move instantly and swiftly. Thus, the body has developed an effective protective mechanism against potentially harmful situations.

2.5. ANALYSIS OF TENSIONS ASSOCIATED WITH MUSCLE CONTRACTION

The EMG (electromyography) signal obtained from a single motor unit can vary significantly due to factors such as muscle condition and fatigue. In particular, peripheral neuropathies (nerve injuries) may result in muscles not fully receiving stimuli from nerves. Nerves have the ability to regenerate, allowing for recovery over time. However, signal transmission in regenerated nerve fibers is slower compared to healthy fibers. Additionally, in such neuropathies, the overall nerve conduction velocity decreases due to reduced nerve excitability. As a result, the EMG signal exhibits increased dispersion and synchronization among motor units is disrupted. In Arduino-based EMG systems, the electrical potentials from different motor units during normal muscle contraction are measured. For example, during a mild contraction, the activity of a single motor unit can be clearly detected, whereas as muscle force increases, signals from many motor units overlap, making it difficult to isolate individual units. As the contraction force of the muscle increases, the firing frequency of active motor units also rises, and more motor units are recruited. EMG sensors connected to Arduino detect electrical activity emitted by muscle fibers at the microvolt level and convert these signals into digital form via an analog-to-digital converter for processing. The amplitude of the measured EMG signal depends on factors such as muscle fiber thickness, sensor placement, and the sensor's frequency filtering characteristics (Farina, D., Merletti, R., Enoka, R. M., 2014). Additionally, the duration of the signal is inversely proportional to the conduction velocity of muscle fibers. When multiple motor units are activated simultaneously, the EMG signal collected by Arduino exhibits a complex, composite structure. The sum of components originating from each motor unit can be schematically observed in this signal. Thanks to the Arduino platform, these complex signals can be monitored, recorded, and analyzed in real-time. This method holds significant importance in the evaluation of muscle functions, detection of nerve injuries, and various biomedical applications.

Figure 5. Surface Electromyography (EMG) Signal Processing and Motor Unit Decomposition

2.6. PROTOTYPE OF EMG-BASED PROSTHETIC HAND CONTROL BOARD

In this study, electromyographic (EMG) signals obtained from the human muscular system were interpreted and utilized for controlling a prosthetic hand. The circuit board shown in the figure is a microcontroller-based control and signal processing unit developed specifically for this purpose. This system serves as a platform that both reads and processes EMG signals and generates appropriate control signals for output units (such as servo motors and mechanical fingers) based on the acquired data.

Figure 6. EMG-Based Prosthetic Hand Control Board

Main Components on the Circuit Board:

- **Arduino Nano Microcontroller:** Serves as the core of the system, processing and filtering EMG signals and converting them into appropriate control commands. It also manages digital and analog data exchange.
- **4-Digit Display V1.2:** Provides a visual output of digital data corresponding to muscle activity or information such as time and power level. It is specifically designed for easy data tracking during experimental analyses.
- **Potentiometer (Analog Input):** Used to adjust analog parameters such as the gain control of EMG signals or manual setting of movement speed.

- **DC-DC Voltage Regulator Module:** Supplies the required stable voltage level to maintain system operation. It safely steps down the input voltage to the desired level to power the Arduino and other components.
- **Mini Buzzer (Audible Alert Module):** Included to generate sound alerts in case of system errors or to provide feedback for specific commands.
- **USB-UART Converter (FTDI Module):** Facilitates serial communication between the Arduino Nano and a computer, enabling software updates, data logging, and analysis.

This board operates sensitively to EMG signals and is specifically designed for use in biomechanical simulations, controlling prosthetic hand movements, robotic systems based on muscle activity, and educational applications involving bioelectrical signals. The system has the potential to generate motor commands depending on the type of muscle movement and contraction intensity. This capability enables the prosthetic hand's fingers to move naturally and in coordination based on real-time muscle signals from the user. This prototype also serves as a foundational platform for human-prosthesis interface and control algorithm studies. The developed hardware, used in conjunction with simulation software, represents an important intermediate step toward real-world applications.

2.7. SIMULATION OF MUSCLE ACTIVITY USING EMG SIGNALS

The above graph illustrates the relationship between the EMG signal and muscle activity:

Purple curve: Represents the raw (input) EMG signal.

Orange curve: Represents the muscle activity data obtained after rectification and smoothing of the EMG signal.

Formula Descriptions:

Raw EMG Signal:

$$\text{EMG}(t) = A \cdot \sin(2\pi ft) + \text{noise} \quad (1)$$

Here:

A: Amplitude

f: Frequency (Hz)

t: Time (seconds) *Rectify (Mutlak değer):*

$$| \text{EMG}(t) | \quad (2)$$

(Smoothing):

Using a moving average filter:

$$\text{Muscle activity } (t) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} | \text{EMG } (t - i) | \quad (3)$$

Here, **N** is the filter window length.

3. RESULTS

In this study, a fundamental control infrastructure was developed for a prosthetic hand system operating based on muscle activity in the human arm and hand, alongside hardware and software infrastructure for processing and evaluating electromyographic (EMG) signals. The developed system interprets EMG signals obtained from the user and forms the basis of an artificial hand prototype aimed at mimicking the natural finger movements performed by the biological hand.

Within the scope of the study:

The raw and processed (rectified and smoothed) forms of EMG signals were comparatively analyzed. A custom Arduino-based control and display board was designed, successfully integrating real-time data acquisition, processing, and visualization functions. Digital data corresponding to muscle activity were converted using a control algorithm prepared to interface with servo motors. Due to its low cost, portability, and extensibility, the developed system provides a suitable platform for both academic research and the development of prototype systems for rehabilitation purposes. Consequently, this study represents a significant step in the development of prosthetic hand systems based on muscle activity, successfully offering an infrastructure that enables human-prosthesis interaction to be more precise, natural, and effective. Future goals include enhancing the system with advanced machine learning algorithms and achieving more precise control through multi-channel EMG systems.

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